

Center for Composite Materials

Electrophoretic Deposition of Carbon Nanotubes on Highly Aligned Discontinuous Carbon Fibers

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OUTLINE

- **Introduction**
- **Carbon Fiber Composites: Piezo-resistivity**
- **Electrophoretic Deposition of Carbon Nanotubes**
- **Piezoresistivity of Carbon Nanotube coated Carbon Fiber Composite**
- **Conclusions and Future Work**

Carbon Fiber Composite

- **High-performance** material
- **High modulus**
- **Electrically** and thermally **conductive**
- Carbon fiber composite **shows piezoresistivity**
- **Used in aerospace, automotive, electronics, etc.**

Sayam et al, Carbon Letters (2022) 32:1173-1205

Piezoresistivity of Carbon Fiber Composites

- Fiber **orientation**
- Fiber **volume fraction**
- Carbon **fiber type**/ fiber **breakage** and **cracking**
- Polymer/ matrix type
- **Tunneling** effect/ percolation network
- **Contact resistance**
- **Continuous** or **short** carbon fiber

Continuous Fiber Composite

Short Fiber Composite

Carbon Nanotubes (CNT)

- **CNT composites** are piezo-resistive
- Electrically **conductive networks** at low concentration
- **Contact resistance** between CNTs dominates
- **Contact resistance** increases with **tunneling gap**
- **Resistance changes** with **strain**

Hu et al, Acta Materialia 56 (2008)

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Factors Influencing Resistance Change

- Piezo-resistivity of carbon fiber
- Direct contact / tunneling effect

Continuous and Discontinuous Fiber Composites

- **Continuous** carbon fiber composite

Prepreg IM7 / 977-3

SYENSQO (MFG 040423)

Continuous Carbon Fiber Composite

- **Highly aligned discontinuous carbon fiber** composites

Fiber – IM7 (3-5 mm)

Resin - SYENSQO 977-3

- Used **autoclave** for consolidation/curing

Highly Aligned Discontinuous Carbon Fiber Composite

Uniaxial Tension Test Setup

Fracture Behavior

Aligned Discontinuous Carbon Fiber Composites

Continuous Carbon Fiber Composites

Gauge Factor (Sensitivity) Comparison

Sample (#)	GF
TuFF / 977-3	~ 2.0
Cont. / 977-3	~ 5.5

Continuous fiber composite is **more sensitive** to tensile deformation than aligned discontinuous fiber composites

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Electrophoretic Deposition of CNT

Electrophoretic Deposition Setup

- CNTs are **functionalized** with polyethyleneimine (PEI)
- **Aqueous dispersion** and CNTs deposits using **direct current** at **room temperature**
- A **thin film** ($<1 \mu\text{m}$) of PEI functionalized nanotubes is created
- Can coat **conductive/ non-conductive** fabric/ fibers

CNT Coating Through EPD

20 seconds

Before
Compression

5 min

After
Compression

- **Film thickness** can be **controlled**
- CNT film is **porous** and **compressible**
- CNT film makes fiber **electrically conductive** and **piezoresistive**

Film Thickness Variation

Porous and Compressible

Doshi Sagar, 2020 University of Delaware

CNT Coating on Carbon Fiber

EPD Setup

Electrode for Carbon Fibers EPD

SEM image of Carbon Fiber after EPD

Specimen and Testing

Schematic of the Specimen for Uniaxial Stretch

Test Setup for Uniaxial Stretch

Piezoresistivity of CNT Coated Fibers

GF ~ 1.7

Uncoated Single Fiber

GF > 25

CNT coated Single Fiber

- Significant **increase** in **gauge factor** after CNT coating
- **Failure strain** of CNT-coated fiber is 10% of that of the uncoated fiber
- CNT film **may improve** the piezo-resistivity of highly aligned discontinuous carbon fiber composites

EPD of Aligned Discontinuous Carbon Fibers

Electrophoretic Deposition Setup

- Fibers/ fabric should maintain **contact with the cathode** for appropriate CNT deposition
- Fibers during the deposition **should not move** during the process and while transferring to the oven for drying
- **Alignment** of carbon fiber must be maintained to retain the mechanical properties of the composite.

EPD of Aligned Discontinuous Carbon Fibers

EPD Setup

Aligned Discontinuous Fibers on Electrode for EPD

After 5 min in CNT Dispersion

- The aligned discontinuous fiber sheet is kept on the carrier fabric for EPD
- Aligned discontinuous fibers are **removed** with dispersion during deposition
- Some mechanism is required to **hold the fibers**
 - Covered by carrier fabric
 - Covered under nylon mesh

Covering by Carrier Fabric

EPD Setup – Aligned Discontinuous Fiber Sheet Covered by Carrier Fabric

SEM Image of Carbon Fiber after EPD

Covering by Carrier Fabric- Challenges

- Carbon nanotube **film starts growing** from the electrode to the carbon fibers
- **Transferring** from the electrode to the oven for drying is difficult
- **Fiber alignment is compromised**

Fiber's Alignment after EPD

Nylon Mesh Covering

EPD Setup – Aligned Discontinuous Fiber Sheet Under Nylon Mesh

SEM Image of Aligned Discontinuous Fiber Sheet after EPD

EPD of ADF Under Nylon mesh

Optical Micrograph after EPD

- **Easy transfer** from the electrode to the oven
- Discontinuous fiber **alignment is maintained** except at the boundary
- Nylon mesh **holds the fiber in place** throughout the EPD process
- Can be applied to larger aligned discontinuous carbon fiber sheets

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EPD of Aligned Discontinuous Carbon Fiber

EPD Setup

Electrode for EPD of Aligned Discontinuous Fiber Sheet

SEM Image of Aligned Discontinuous Fiber Sheet after EPD

Nylon mesh is used to keep discontinuous fibers aligned and intact with the electrodes during EPD process.

Test Specimen Preparation

Schematic of Prepreg and Composite panel manufacturing

Composite Panel

Specimen with End Tab

Effect of CNT Coating

Coated Uncoated

Specimen Number:	Electrical Resistance (Ohm)				
	R1-1'	R2-2'	R3-3'	R2-3'	R2'-3'
UC1	10.8	23.5	42.7	36	37.7
UC2	12.1	17.1	41.5	28.5	31
UC3	10.5	23.3	41.2	26.7	40.8
UC4	8.6	14.3	32.5	18.9	28.3
UC5	10.2	19	41.3	31	33
C1	2.7	7	5.8	5.8	6.6
C2	2.3	5.1	7.1	4.8	8.4
C3	1.9	5.1	5.1	5.3	10.2
C4	2.4	5.1	5.3	4.1	6.3
C5	3.4	4	3.6	4.2	4.7
C6	3.8	6.8	4.6	4.5	7

- **Resistance decreases** due to the CNT coating on carbon fibers
- **Cross resistance is high** (R2-3' & R2'-3)
- **Cross-resistance is high**, possibly due to the composite being prepared under vacuum (not in an autoclave)

Specimen for Tensile Testing

- **200 gsm** aligned discontinuous fiber fabric is used with **2 layer of 50 gsm** 977-3 to make prepreg
- Volume fraction ~ **55+ %**
- Specimen size 120 mm x 12.5 mm x 0.7 mm
- Specimens made with EPD coated, aligned discontinuous fibers sheets are approximately **5% thicker**

Tensile Test Setup

Piezoresistivity Comparison

- Uncoated specimen shows **higher piezoresistivity**
- CNT coating **improves the conductivity**; but, it **decreases the piezo resistivity**
- Carbon fibers are conductive and it make coating to start directly on top surface
- Possibly **no CNT coating** on intermediate carbon fibers

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Conclusions and Future Work

- Carbon nanotube **improves the piezoresistivity** of carbon fibers; however, **decrease the failure strain**
- **Electrophoretic deposition** on aligned discontinuous carbon fibers is possible **with control of the fibers' movement** in the dispersion during the process
- In an aligned carbon fiber composite, carbon nanotube coating **does not improve** the piezoresistivity
- In EPD process, possibly **there is no CNT coating** on all carbon fibers through thickness
- **AC EPD** can improve the CNT film growth of carbon fibers through thickness

